

USAGE OF SURROGATE MUSCLE MODELS IN ECHOCARDIOGRAPHY-BASED LEFT VENTRICLE MODEL

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Abstract

This abstract presents a comprehensive overview of advancements in the development of surrogate models for cardiomyopathy, with a primary emphasis on emulating the Huxley-type muscle model while addressing computational demands [1-5]. Employing a combination of data-driven and physics-informed methodologies, the authors employ deep neural networks specifically trained to precisely obtain stress and stiffness within the finite element cardiac analysis. A comparative analysis reveals similarities between the stresses obtained with surrogate and original models, underscoring the computational efficiency inherent in the surrogate approach.

In light of these promising findings, the abstract underscores the transformative potential of machine learning-based surrogate models in computational modeling for cardiomyopathy, particularly in the realm of multiscale simulations. The efficacy of the surrogate models, demonstrated through their ability to closely replicate the behavior of the Huxley model while significantly reducing computational overhead, enables their practical and clinical usage.

Moreover, we display the application of surrogate models in cardiac cycle simulations of left ventricle, with model being generated from on the echocardiographic images. This expansion aims to highlight the versatility of methodology, showcasing its adaptability in capturing characteristics specific to diverse cardiac structures. This extension not only amplifies the robustness of the surrogate models but also underscores their potential to contribute significantly to a more nuanced and comprehensive understanding of cardiac dynamics across various anatomical components.

References

1. Stojanovic B, Svcevic M, Kaplarevic-Malistic A, Gilbert R, Mijailovich S, Multi-scale striated muscle contraction model linking sarcomere length-dependent cross-bridge kinetics to macroscopic deformation, *Journal of Computational Science*, 39(-):101062, 2020.
2. Stojanovic B, Svcevic M, Kaplarevic-Malistic A, Ivanovic M, Nedic D, Filipovic N, Mijailovich S, Coupling finite element and huxley models in multiscale muscle modeling, 2015 IEEE 15th International Conference on Bioinformatics and Bioengineering (BIBE). IEEE, 2015.
3. Milicevic B, Ivanovic M, Stojanovic B, Milosevic M, Kojic M, Filipovic N, Huxley muscle model surrogates for high-speed multi-scale simulations of cardiac contraction, *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 149(-):105963, 2022.
4. Milicevic B, Simic V, Milosevic M, Ivanovic M, Stojanovic B, Kojic M, Filipovic N, Integration of Surrogate Huxley Muscle Model into Finite Element Solver for Simulation of the Cardiac Cycle, 44th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC), 2022.
5. Raissi M, Perdikaris P, Karniadakis G, Physics-informed neural networks: A deep learning framework for solving forward and inverse problems involving nonlinear partial differential equations, *Journal of Computational Physics*, 378(-):686–707, 2019.

Acknowledgements

The research was supported by the STRATIFYHF project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101080905. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or granting authority - European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This research was also supported by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia, contract number [451-03-68/2023-14/200107 (Faculty of Engineering, University of Kragujevac) and 451-03-68/2023-14/200378 (Institute of Information Technologies, University of Kragujevac)]. The authors acknowledge support from the City of Kragujevac, Serbia.

